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Evaluation of Grit, General Weighted Average, and Year Level among NU Fairview College Students

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Abstract

The concept of grit, defined as passion and perseverance towards long-term goals, has gained attention in educational research. Grit influences academic performance by driving individuals to overcome setbacks. A study was conducted on NU Fairview college students across different year levels, comparing their general weighted average (GWA) and level of grit. A quantitative study with 375 college students utilized a 12-item Grit Scale. Grit levels did not significantly vary among year levels, but the general weighted average did. Results show that there is a significant relationship between grit level and GWA. Higher levels of grit correlated with higher year level. Further research is needed to explore the relationship between grit and academic success in Asian populations. Recommendations include fostering grit through targeted interventions could enhance student outcomes.

Keywords: *grit, college, year level, general weighted average, academic setting*

Introduction

The concept of grit, defined as passion and perseverance towards long-term goals, has gained significant attention in educational research. College students often encounter various challenges in their academic journey, mainly due to the transition from high school, compared to college where there is a greater emphasis on self-monitoring and independent learning (Gentry, 2012). Grit has been identified as a potential factor influencing academic performance, as it drives individuals to overcome setbacks and persist in the face of adversity (Duckworth, 2016).

While previous research has explored the relationship between grit and academic achievement, empirical studies specifically investigating the impact of grit on students' performance or general weighted average (GWA) still need to be expanded. The existing literature lacks a definitive consensus on how strongly grit correlates with academic success (Morell et al., 2021), and there is a notable gap in empirical studies examining the role of grit in the academic context, particularly in Asia (Datu et al., 2016).

Moreover, the findings from previous studies on the correlation between grit and academic performance have been somewhat mixed, with some studies indicating a strong correlation (Muenks et al., 2018) and others reporting a weaker association (Steinmayr et al., 2018). These inconsistent results have further emphasized the need for further investigation into this topic.

Research Objectives

This study has the following objectives: to identify the year levels of NU Fairview college students, determine the general weighted average (GWA) across each year level, assess the level of grit among students at different year levels, examine significant differences in grit and GWA among students at different year levels, and explore the relationship between grit and GWA among students. By achieving these objectives, the study aims to contribute insights into the role of grit in academic performance and provide valuable information for interventions and support to enhance student success.

Methodology

The research design employed in this study was a non-experimental quantitative cross-sectional design, aiming to analyze the differences in grit and general weighted average (GWA) among college students at different year levels. Convenience sampling was utilized to select participants from NU Fairview, with a total target sample size of 375 students determined using Slovin's formula. The study collected data using a 12-item grit scale questionnaire developed by Angela Duckworth. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the data, while Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was employed to compare grit and GWA among year levels. Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r) was utilized to assess the relationship between grit and GWA. Ethical considerations were taken into account, and participants provided informed consent before data collection.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. Demographics of the NU Fairview Students

<i>Year Level</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
First Year	125	33.33
Second Year	125	33.33
Third Year	125	33.33
Total	375	100

Table 1 presents an overview of the characteristics of the participants in terms of their demographics. According to the table provided earlier, the sample for this study consisted of individuals from three distinct year levels. The total number of participants included in

the study was 375. Moreover, the researchers evenly divided these participants, with 125 individuals representing each year level.

Table 2. General Weighted Average of the Respondents

<i>Year Level</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>
First Year	3.17	0.42
Second Year	3.28	0.57
Third Year	2.87	0.64

Table 2 presents the mean values of the general weighted average (GWA) for each year level of the respondents. The first-year students had an average GWA of 3.17, while the second-year students had a higher average of 3.28. In contrast, the third-year students had the lowest average GWA of 2.87. This observation suggests that second-year students perform better academically on average, indicating their familiarity with university requirements and effective learning and time management strategies. This finding aligns with Dweck's theory on the growth mindset, where individuals who believe in their ability to improve through hard work tend to embrace challenges and achieve greater success (Dweck, 2006). Conversely, the decrease in average GWA among third-year students raises concerns about their academic performance, possibly due to increased workload, higher academic standards, or external pressures. Further investigation is necessary to identify the factors contributing to this decline and develop appropriate interventions to support third-year students in improving their academic achievement.

Table 3. Grit Level of Students

<i>Year Level</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
First Year	3.15	0.54	Average
Second Year	3.14	0.58	Average
Third Year	3.24	0.49	Average

Table 3 presents the level of grit of the respondents at each year level. Based on the computation, the researchers obtained the following values for the first, second, and third-year students, respectively: 3.15, 3.14, and 3.24. Based on the observation, the highest mean level of grit came from the third-year students, while first-year and second-year students' grit levels are not comparatively far from each other. The mean averages of the outcomes fall into the average section in the range of 2.50 to 3.49 based on the reference scale of grit (Gemepino, n.d.). As indicated by Gemepino (n.d.), they are described as somewhat gritty, possessing an average passion and perseverance for long-term goals but can be discouraged by setbacks. As the results revealed that third-year college students have the highest means out of the three, this phenomenon could be explained that one of the factors is age (Salud, 2022).

Table 4. Difference Between Grit of Students per Year Level

<i>Source of Variation</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>P-Value</i>	<i>F-crit</i>
Between Groups	0.84	2	0.42	1.46	0.23	3.02
Within Groups	107.16	372	0.29			
Total	108.00	374				

Table 4 displays the outcomes of the analysis of variance (ANOVA) conducted on the grit levels of students from various academic levels. ANOVA is a statistical method utilized to evaluate significant variations in a given variable across multiple groups. The variable under investigation pertains to the level of grit, while the groups being compared are the distinct year levels of students. The table above presents various statistical parameters. The F-value acquired in this instance is 1.46, with a corresponding p-value of 0.23. Given that the p-value exceeds the threshold of 0.05, it can be concluded that there is no statistically significant indication to support the notion that the mean levels of grit exhibit significant variation across the different year levels and that grit is considered a crucial personal resource for college students (Mason, 2018). The null hypothesis shall be deemed not rejected.

Table 5. Difference Between GWA of Students per Year Level

<i>Source of Variation</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>P-Value</i>	<i>F-crit</i>
Between Groups	11.21	2	5.61	18.34	0.00	3.01
Within Groups	113.69	372	0.31			
Total	124.91	374				

Table 5 exhibits the outcomes of an ANOVA that was performed to investigate the variations in the General Weighted Average (GWA) of students among various academic years. The p-value for the aforementioned factor has been computed and is presented in Table 3. The F-value acquired in this instance is 18.34, which is larger than the F crit 3.02, while the corresponding p-value is 0.00, indicating a statistically significant outcome. By comparing the p-value to the predetermined significance level of 0.05, it can be inferred that there is a significant variation in the GWA across different academic levels of students. In light of the findings presented in the table, it can be concluded that there exist statistically significant variations in the GWA of students across varying academic years, and absolute age might have a favorable impact on persistence in effort (Peña & Duckworth, 2018). The null hypothesis, which posits the absence of statistically significant differences, may be refuted.

The correlation analysis revealed in table 6 with a weak positive relationship between grit and GWA, with a correlation coefficient of

0.12. This finding aligns with previous studies that also reported small to moderate correlations between grit and academic achievement (Reysen et al., 2019; Lam & Zhou, 2022). It is important to note that correlation does not imply causation, as the measurement only reflects the magnitude and direction of the association between variables.

Table 6. *Relationship Between Grit and GWA*

	<i>df</i>	<i>Pearson correlation</i>	<i>P-Value</i>
Grit Level and GWA	373	0.12	0.02

Conclusion

This study highlights the need for further research on the connection between grit and academic performance, particularly in Asian populations. Existing empirical studies have failed to establish a definitive generalization regarding this connection (Datu et al., 2016). While no significant variance in grit levels was found across different academic years, targeted interventions and comprehensive strategies are necessary to support students at each grade level. These findings underscore the importance of specialized interventions and support plans for students (Peña & Duckworth, 2018). The study supports the integration of grit and power concepts, suggesting that students embodying both traits are more likely to achieve exceptional grades (Glasser Institute for Choice Theory, n.d.)

These findings contribute to understanding factors influencing academic achievement and inform educational practices for improved outcomes. The study confirms a weak positive correlation between grit level and GWA (Reysen et al., 2019), emphasizing the importance of considering additional factors like study habits and motivation in understanding academic success.

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